

Supplementary Figure S1. Patient-level attention map for an IDH-WT patient correctly classified.

Supplementary Figure S2. Patient-level attention map for an IDH-Mutant 1p/19q-intact patient correctly classified.

Supplementary Figure S3. Patient-level attention map for an IDH-Mutant 1p/19q-codel patient correctly classified.

Supplementary Figure S4. Patient-level attention map for an IDH-WT patient misclassified as IDH-Mutant 1p/19q-intact.

Supplementary Figure S5. Patient-level attention map for an IDH-Mutant 1p/19q-intact patient misclassified as IDH-Mutant 1p/19q-codel.

Supplementary Figure S6. Patient-level attention map for an IDH-Mutant 1p/19q-codel patient misclassified as IDH-WT.

Parameters	Values
Batch size	2
Epoch number	80
Optimizer	SGD
Scheduler	Polynomial
Input modalities	[T1-Gd, FLAIR]; [T1-Gd, FLAIR, T2-w]; [T1-Gd, FLAIR, T1-w]; [T1-Gd, FLAIR, T1-w, T2-w]
Network	ResNet-10; ResNet-18; ResNet-34
Dropout size	0.3; 0.5; 0.7
Optimizer weight decay	3e-04; 3e-05; 3e-06
Learning rate	1e-03; 1e-04; 1e-05

Supplementary Table S1. Hyperparameters selected during the optimization phase of both modules.